

Utility of CBNAAT as an Adjunct to Conventional Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology in Presumptive Diagnosis of Tuberculous Lymphadenitis at a Tertiary Care Hospital in South India: An Observational Study

R. Shobija¹, G. Sangamithra², Arasi Rajesh³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Thoothukudi Medical College, Tamilnadu, India

²Professor and Head, Department of Respiratory Medicine, Government Thoothukudi Medical College, Tamilnadu, India

³Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Government Thoothukudi Medical College, Tamilnadu, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. R.Shobija

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Abstract:

Introduction: The most common extrapulmonary manifestation of tuberculosis (TB) is Tuberculous lymphadenitis. Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis is challenging due to the pauci bacillary nature of the disease and limited tests. The role of Cartridge based Nucleic Acid Amplification test (CBNAAT) in the diagnosis of lymphnode TB combined with Conventional Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) helps in early identification of Rifampicin resistant cases and initiating treatment at the earliest.

Aim: To determine the significance of CBNAAT as an adjunct to Conventional FNAC to diagnose extrapulmonary Tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods: This cross sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Pathology in collaboration with the Department of Respiratory Medicine at Government Thoothukudi Medical College Hospital, Tamilnadu, India for a period of 12 months (from January 2023 to December 2023) on 120 samples of Head and Neck palpable lymph node lesions. From the fine needle aspirates smears were prepared for Haematoxylin and Eosin staining. The residual material from the aspirate will be rinsed into normal saline in Falcon tube, incubated at room temperature and processed for CBNAAT testing. The results were analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 21.0.

Results: A total of 120 cases were included in the final analysis. In our study youngest patient was 10 months and oldest was 65 years. Female preponderance was noted. Maximum number of cases was in 3rd decade. Out of 35 cases with FNAC findings favouring EPTB, 9 were CBNAAT positive and 26 were CBNAAT negative. Out of 85 cases with negative FNA findings, CBNAAT was positive in 1 case. The sensitivity of CBNAAT in our study was 25.7% and specificity was 98.8%. Positive predictive value was 90%, Negative predictive value was 76.3% and Diagnostic accuracy was 77.5%.

Conclusion: CBNAAT can be added with FNAC to get more specific results. Use of CBNAAT alone for diagnosis of EPTB may result in missing the diagnosis. Combined modality incorporating FNAC and CBNAAT is the best approach for diagnosis of EPTB.

Keywords: Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis, CBNAAT, Lymphadenitis, Aspirates.

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Introduction

In the developing world, tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the most common chronic granulomatous infections. Globally, the prevalence of TB was estimated to be 10.5 million, of which 1.8 million new cases arise annually in India, accounting for nearly 40% of India's population being infected with TB [1]. Tuberculosis is an infectious systemic disease caused by the species *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* bacteria, which

commonly affects lungs (pulmonary TB) and other organs (extrapulmonary TB). Extra pulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB) is defined according to WHO classification criteria as an infection by *M. tuberculosis* which affects tissues and organs outside the pulmonary parenchyma [2]. EPTB is an equally important manifestation of TB which remains undiagnosed due to diagnostic challenges in developing countries. EPTB most frequently

manifests as peripheral lymphadenopathy and it can involve any organ of the body including brain, skin, soft tissues, small and large intestine, appendix and genitourinary tract [3]. Cervical lymphadenopathy is abnormal enlargement of lymph nodes (LNs) in the head and neck region usually >1 cm. The majority of cases are benign in nature but the differential diagnosis can be broad. Tuberculous lymphadenopathy is the most frequent type of EPTB, accounting for 35% of all cases [4]. As the extrapulmonary sites are mostly smear negative, it is believed that these cases are less contagious and thus early diagnosis and timely treatment is required in these cases to prevent further spread and reduce mortality [5]. The samples from extrapulmonary infection will have low bacterial count as compared with sputum specimens [6].

FNAC is a rapid, simple, and widely used diagnostic test in evaluating lymphadenopathy. It is a rapid diagnostic technique but has very low Sensitivity due to its paucicellular nature [7]. Ancillary tests like ZN stain and Auramine and Rhodamine stain on FNA material aid in diagnosis. Both FNAC and smear microscopy cannot identify species and drug resistance. There are few limitations of FNAC like subjectivity of the test, failure to differentiate between various granulomatous diseases and absence of granuloma in immunocompromised patients. There are also limitations of diagnosing EPTB by ZN staining like less sensitivity. Positive smear requires more than 5,000 to 10,000 bacilli/ml and hence it has limited diagnostic value in majority of EPTB samples [8]. In resource-poor countries like India, Gold standard Mycobacterial culture and drug susceptibility testing are not always available, and their results take four to eight weeks or even longer [9].

To overcome all these limitations a rapid and reliable method Cartridge Based Nucleic Acid Amplification Test (CBNAAT)/GeneXpert MTB/RIF1 (Cepheid, USA) was endorsed by WHO in 2010 for use in TB laboratories. It was introduced in INDIA by Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP) in 2012 as a pilot project in Maharashtra [10].

GeneXpert MTB-RIF is a real-time nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT) that simultaneously detects the DNA of MTB and the *rpoB* mutation associated with rifampicin resistance. It requires minimal technical expertise and has a turnaround time of less than 2 h. It can be readily performed on the aspirated samples for detection of MTB and helps in ruling out other cytomorphological mimics. Also ability of CBNAAT to detect as low bacterial load as 100-130 bacilli per ml of sample compared to 10^4 per ml for ZN staining makes it ideal for paucibacillary tuberculosis. CBNAAT is at par with culture which demands 100 bacilli per ml of sample [11]. Currently CBNAAT is the first

mode of investigation in key population group like Children, HIV positive patients, EPTB.

This study was undertaken to assess the role of CBNAAT using FNA material in the diagnosis of tubercular lymphadenopathy and to compare it with cytology results.

Aims and Objectives

1. To do comparison of lymph node aspirate CBNAAT and Cytology via FNAC for diagnosis of tuberculous lymphadenitis.
2. To determine the significance of CBNAAT as an adjunct to Conventional FNAC to diagnose extrapulmonary Tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods:

- **Study Design:** Hospital based Prospective study.
- **Study Center:** Cytology section of Department of Pathology and Respiratory Medicine Department, Government Thoothukudi Medical College, Tamil Nadu, India.
- **Study Participants:** All presumptive cases of tubercular lymphadenitis.
- **Age Group:** This study includes all age groups.
- **Study Duration:** One year (January 2023 to December 2023).
- **Sample Size:** 120 cases.
- Prior approval from Institutional ethics committee was taken with IEC Ref No.03/2023-03.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients of either sex, of all age groups with palpable Head and Neck Lymph node swellings
2. Patients who are willing to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

1. Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis patients who were already on treatment
2. Scant aspirate in whose case material could not be sent for CBNAAT
3. Patients who are not willing to participate

Study Procedure

After explaining the FNAC procedure and complications, written informed consent from all the patients and guardians in case of children were taken. Under aseptic precautions, the FNAC was done by passing a 22-gauge needle attached to a 5 mL syringe into lymph node under two finger guidance, with suction applied, needle was moved back and fro around 10-15 times. Procedure was repeated from same node or other node if material obtained was unsatisfactory. At the time of specimen collection, clinical details were recorded through the patient's clinical records, and the gross

appearance of the aspirate of FNAC specimens were collected. Material obtained was smeared for cytology and remaining aspirate was flushed with

normal saline to empty contents in syringe and hub into Falcon's tube for CBNAAT.

Figure 1: XPERT MTB/RIF CEPHEID

Detection of TB by CB-NAAT was done by Xpert MTB/RIF assay, made by Cepheid. The specimens were processed according to the Gene Xpert system operator manual given by Central TB division, Government of India, Guidance document for the use of CB-NAAT under Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP). The instrument contains 4 cartridges to process 4 samples at each run. According to the standard operating procedure, the assay sample reagent (containing NaOH and isopropanol) was added in 2:1 ratio to the sample and kept for 15 minutes at room temperature with intermittent shaking. Three ml of this treated sample was then transferred to the cartridge and the cartridge was inserted into the module of CB-NAAT instrument. An automatic process completes the remaining assay steps and the results were displayed on the monitor of Gene Xpert after 1 hour and 50 minutes [12].

Xpert MTB/RIF cartridge is a disposable, single self-enclosed test unit in which all steps of CB-NAAT, i.e., sample processing, PCR amplification and detection are automated and integrated. The manual steps involved in the assay are adding the reagent and sample loading. The test procedure is made biosafe by tuberculocidal property of the assay's sample reagent [13,14]. The FNAC criteria for diagnosis of tuberculosis are the presence of

clusters of epithelioid cells with or without giant cells and/ or caseous necrosis [15].

The CB-NAAT result is displayed as positive or negative in the CB-NAAT software. It provides a semiquantitative estimate of the concentration of bacilli as defined by the cycle threshold (Ct) range (high, <16; medium, 16-22; low, 22-28; very low, >28). The FNAC data was recorded in FNAC register, Department of Pathology and CB-NAAT data was recorded in CB-NAAT register of the Respiratory Medicine Department.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from our study was compiled and tabulated on MS excel work-sheet and master table were made accordingly. Suitable charts and diagrams were made for better presentation to analyze the data and conclusion was drawn accordingly. Statistical significance taken as $p < 0.05$. IBM SPSS version 21 was used for statistical analysis.

Results

Total of 120 subjects were included in the final analysis for FNAC and CBNAAT. In our study, youngest patient was 10 months and oldest was 65 years. Majority of the cases were in between 21-30 years age group with female preponderance [Table 1].

Table 1: Age and sex wise distribution of cases

Age group (years)	No. of cases	Males	Females
<1-10	19	7	12
11-20	13	7	6
21-30	44	18	26
31-40	16	6	10
41-50	9	3	6

51-60	13	5	8
61-70	6	3	3
Total	120	49	71

Majority of the CBNAAT positive cases were in between 21-30 years age group with female preponderance [Table/Fig-3]

Table 2: Age and sex wise distribution of CBNAAT positive cases

Age group (years)	Total	Males	Females
<1-10	0	0	0
11-20	2	1	1
21-30	6	1	5
31-40	1	0	1
41-50	1	1	0
51-60	0	0	0
61-70	0	0	0
Total	10	3	7

In the present study, majority of the cases (68.3%) had fever as associated symptom along with lymphadenopathy followed by cough (37.5%) and weight loss (20.8%), respectively [Fig-2].

Figure 2: Clinical presentation of cases

Most common aspirate encountered while doing FNAC was blood mixed accounting for 65.8% of the total out of which 1.26% cases were CBNAAT positive while cheesy aspirate signifying tuberculosis was seen in 15% of the total cases out of which 11.1% cases were CBNAAT positive [Table 3].

Table 3: Distribution of type of FNA aspirates along with CBNAAT results (n=120).

Type of aspirate	Total	CBNAAT positive	CBNAAT negative
Purulent	27 (22.5%)	7 (25.9%)	20
Cheesy	18 (15%)	2 (11.1%)	12
Blood mixed	79 (65.8%)	1 (1.26%)	78
Total	120	10	110

The diagnosis of FNAC of 120 cases were reactive lymphoid hyperplasia, suppurative lesion (Table/Figure 3), epithelioid granuloma without necrosis (Table/Figure 4), epithelioid granuloma with necrosis (Table/Figure 5), caseous necrosis without epithelioid cells, Metastatic Carcinomatous deposits and lymphoma and their proportion were 38.3%, 24.1%, 15%, 8.3%, 5.8%, 5.8% and 2.5% respectively. (Table /Figure 6)

Figure 3: Suppurative lesion-Smear shows sheets of polymorphs

Figure 4: Epithelioid granuloma without necrosis-Smear shows a granuloma composed of epithelioid cells with no necrosis in the background [H&E stain 40X]

Figure 5: Epithelioid granuloma with necrosis-Smear shows granuloma composed of epithelioid cells with necrotic background [H&E stain 40X]

Table 4: Descriptive analysis of FNA features in the study population (n=120)

FNA features	Frequency	Percentage
Reactive lymphoid hyperplasia	46	38.3%
Suppurative lesion	29	24.16%
Epithelioid Granuloma without necrosis	18	15%
Epithelioid Granuloma with necrosis	10	8.33%
Caseous necrosis without epithelioid cells	7	5.83%
Metastatic carcinomatous deposits	7	5.83%
Lymphoproliferative disorder	3	2.5%
Total	120	100%

Out of 35 cases with FNAC findings favouring EPTB, 9 were CB-NAAT positive (Table/Figure 9) and 26 were CB-NAAT negative.

Out of 85 cases with negative FNA findings, CB-NAAT was positive in 1 case. This case showed features of suppurative lesion in FNAC. This is one reason why we recommend the use of XPERT in any purulent aspirate irrespective of clinical suspicion as the epithelioid granulomas and

caseation may not be visible in the presence of suppuration.

Compared to FNAC, CBNAAT showed sensitivity of 25.7%, specificity of 98.8%, false positive rate of 1.17%, false negative rate of 74.2%, Positive predictive value (PPV) of 90%, Negative Predictive Value (NPV) 76.3% and diagnostic accuracy of 77.5%.

Table 5: Diagnostic performance of CBNAAT versus FNAC

CBNAAT	FNAC Positive	FNAC Negative	Total
Positive	9(25.7%)	1(1.17%)	10
Negative	26(74.28%)	84(98.8%)	110
Total	35	85	120

Discussion

The present study is a hospital based prospective observational study in the diagnosis of suspected tubercular lymphadenopathy by CBNAAT and then we compare it with FNAC results. This study aimed to assess the applicability of CBNAAT in early diagnosis of TB lymphadenopathy and early identification of MDR-TB. FNAC being an OPD

procedure, inexpensive and minimally invasive, it is routinely used now-a-days for diagnosing extrapulmonary TB.

In comparing age and gender-wise distribution of CBNAAT positive cases with other studies, it was found that the younger age group was affected more with female predominance, which correlated with other studies (Tables/Figures 6 and 7).

Table 6: Comparison of age-wise distribution of CBNAAT positive cases with other studies

Study	Age group	Percentage of cases
Present study	21-30	60%
Yassin et al [16].	15-24	30.7%
Aroravk et al [17].	15-24	38%
Brayn et al [18].	15-24	43%
Mulualem et al [19].	16-30	58%

Table 7: Comparison of gender-wise distribution of CBNAAT positive cases with other studies

Study	Male	Female
Present study	30%	70%
Poojasingh et al [20].	31%	69%
Brayn et al [18].	46%	54%
Mulualem et al [19].	67%	76%

FNAC is the preferred investigation of choice for diagnosis in cases of extra pulmonary tuberculosis. Still, they have some limitations, and CBNAAT was developed to overcome these limitations. CBNAAT identifies the targeted rpoB nucleic acid sequences and gives results in about 2 hours. No cross-reaction with other bacterial species was

noted. It is a highly specific test as it uses five unique molecular probes and three specific primers to target rpoB gene for MTB. The present study showed 8.33% CBNAAT positivity. Various studies showed 36% to 96% CBNAAT positivity, as shown in Table /Figure 13 Technical causes like the second or third pass of FNA sent for CBNAAT

and the scanty amount of material sent might be the reasons for low CBNAAT positivity.

Table 8: Comparison of CBNAAT results with other studies

Study	CBNAAT positivity
Shakeel et al. [21]	36.3
Gour et al. [22]	40.0
Srwar et al. [23]	51.7
Moure et al. [24]	58.3
Present study	8.33

On comparison of CBNAAT diagnostic performance of present study (sensitivity 25.7%, specificity 98.8%) with Aruna L et al[25]., (sensitivity-65%, specificity 92.45%), Komanapalli SK et al[26]., (sensitivity 84.25%, specificity 86.71%) Patil SB et al [27]., (sensitivity 55.5%, specificity 83.80%) and Kumar A et al[28]., (sensitivity-92.7%, specificity 98.9%) showed less sensitivity and more specificity. Therefore, FNAC should be included as first line investigation and it should be compared with CBNAAT to get more accurate results and to decrease the chances of missing cases by CBNAAT alone or FNAC alone.

Limitations

1. Sample size was small
2. This was a single centre study

Conclusion

The detectability of Extrapulmonary TB with combination of FNAC and Gene Xpert CBNAAT is very high (85%). Therefore, they may be employed for better and quicker diagnosis of clinically presumptive LNTB patients in resource restricted settings with high EPTB burden.

FNAC is rapid, cost effective highly accurate test in diagnosing tuberculous lymphadenopathy. CBNAAT alone was found less sensitive for blood stained samples than purulent samples. But the present study highlights that FNAC combining it with CBNAAT can add benefit of detection of FNAC missed cases because of purulent material and it is a rapid test available with high specificity. CBNAAT and FNAC testing both are complementary for early diagnosis TB lymphadenopathy and early identification of Rifampicin resistant TB lymphadenopathy. These help in timely diagnosis and treatment of missed TB cases by any single diagnostic test like FNAC and CBNAAT alone. Early diagnosis will help in starting effective treatment on early basis that prevent the further spread of tuberculosis cases in the community and amplify effective utilization of TB control program in our country.

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